

ICCM24

24TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Rapid Manufacturing Pathways for High-Performance Thermoplastic Composites

Mehran Tehrani

Associate Professor

Callaway Golf Endowed Chair

Structural and Materials Engineering

Advanced Composites & Aerospace Structures

August 07, 2025

UC San Diego

Outline

- Introduction to thermoplastic composites and their manufacturing
- In-situ consolidation of thermoplastic composites (TPC)
- Engineered pathways for post-consolidation of TPCs
- Energy-efficient Aerospace-grade Laminates = OATMEAL

Introduction

Matrix: Thermoplastics vs Thermosets

Thermoplastics
Reversible melting

Thermosets
Irreversible curing
(heat or UV activated)

More viscous

Less viscous

These properties affect processing

Additive Manufacturing of TPCs

Material Extrusion (ME)

Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF)

Directed Energy Deposition (DED)

Laser-Assisted Automated Fiber Placement (AFP)

Advanced Manufacturing of Thermoplastic Composites

Part
CAD Model
→
Composite
Material
→

Part →

Out of Autoclave and Rapid Manufacturing

Fast Rate Assembly and Quality Control

Semi-Crystalline Thermoplastic Super-Polymers

PAEKs: superior thermo-mechanical and chemical properties, Max Service Temp. 260°C (500°F)

- PEEK
- PEKK
- LM-PAEK
- PEK

ketone (R-CO-R) and ether groups (R-O-R)

Source: Arkema

Source: Polymers.com

Thermoplastic Composites: Impact damage resistant, weldable (no fasteners or adhesives), easily repairable, fast-rate processing, potentially recyclable.

In-situ consolidation of Thermoplastic Composites

In-House Laser-AFP Test Bed

Bonding Physics

Modelling the AFP Process

Modelling the AFP Process: 50 mm/s

Cooling rates of $>10,000$ °C/min – Repetitive heating results in cold-crystalization

Interlaminar Properties: Degree of Consolidation

ICAT: in-situ consolidation

VBO: Fast AFP + vacuum bag only oven processing

CM: Fast AFP + compression molding

Annealed: Fast AFP + annealing @210°C

Intra-Laminar Properties

E_1
 E_2
 F_1^c
 F_1^t
 F_2^c

Young's modulus in the fiber direction
 Young's modulus in the transverse direction
 compressive strength in the fiber direction
 tensile strength in the fiber direction
 compressive strength in the transverse direction

F_2^t
 $F_{12}^{s0.2}$
 F_{12}^{s5}
 G_{12}

tensile strength in the transverse direction
 in-plane shear strength at offset strain of 0.2 %
 in-plane shear strength at offset strain of 5 %
 in-plane shear modulus

Differences in Structure

- Fiber-polymer interfaces
- Cracks
- Interlaminar and intralaminar voids
- Waviness
- Crystallinity
- Resin rich regions

Engineered Pathways for Post-consolidation of TPCs

Intentional Gaps and Delaminations

Lightly bonded, fast AFP with intentional gaps

Source: CORIOLIS

Part made by AFP

Vacuum bagging oven processing

Final Part with low void content and high SBS

Optimization Procedure

Vacuum bag post-processing

- A. Long VBO (Reference)**
- B. Short VBO #1**
- C. Short VBO #2**
- D. Short VBO #3:**

X-Sectional Microscopy: VBO w/ Engineered Gaps

X-Sectional Microscopy: VBO w/ Engineered Overlaps

C-Scans

Interlaminar Bonding Strength

Out-of-autoclave Amorphous/Crystalline Thermoplastic Materials for Energy-efficient Aerospace-grade Laminates (OATMEAL)

What is OATMEAL?

Out-of-autoclave **A**morphous/semicrystalline **T**hermoplastic **M**aterial for **E**nergy-efficient **A**erospace-grade **L**aminates.

	Tg (°C)	Tm (°C)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)
PEI	220	--	3.4
PEEK	143	343	3.8

Welding Times

	280 °C (s)	320 °C (s)	340 °C (s)	420 °C (s)
PEI	17,155	< 1	--	--
PEEK	NP	NP	592	<1

Remove
excess PEI

Why OATMEAL?

$$T_{\text{melt PEEK}} > T > T_{\text{g PEI}}$$

- Amorphous polymer
 - Semi-crystalline polymer
 - Fiber
- Interlayer
(Resin-rich)

Cooling-rate Agnostic Material

Thickness and SBS

Crystallinity Measurements

